

Research Article

Smart Extension Plug (SMEP)

Azryna Azlen Mohd Nordin^{1,*}, Muhamad Naufal Shairul², and Amyr Farkhan Mohd Armyzy³¹ Kolej Vokasional Shah Alam; g-36367875@moe-dl.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0003-5947-2555² Kolej Vokasional Shah Alam; m-7290458@moe-dl.edu.my³ Kolej Vokasional Shah Alam; m-6741806@moe-dl.edu.my

* Correspondence: g-36367875@moe-dl.edu.my

Abstract: The issue of inefficient electricity consumption among college dormitory residents has prompted the development of the Smart Extension Plug (SMEP) an Internet of Things (IoT) based smart device. SMEP integrates remote control functionality through the Blynk application, real-time voltage and current monitoring also an automatic timer feature. Therefore, several past studies, such as the Smart Plug Prototype, Wi-Fi Smart Plug, and Smart Plug, were compared to produce a more effective and efficient SMEP project. The development of this project utilized the iterative Agile model to ensure the quality and usability of the system. The effectiveness of the SMEP was evaluated through a quantitative survey involving 36 respondents. The data analysis results show that the SMEP successfully improved users' energy management efficiency by 72% while also reducing waste and enhancing safety. This project not only proves the potential of IoT technology in sustainable energy management but also successfully fosters awareness and energy-saving practices among students. Furthermore, the development of IoT technology in the field of energy management can open opportunities for various improvements and the integration of new, more efficient technologies in the future. The SMEP has great potential to be expanded to other institutions to support the national smart energy agenda.

Keywords: SMEP; IoT; Smart Plug; energy management.

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1. INTRODUCTION

College students face several challenges in managing their electrical appliances effectively. They often struggle to control devices such as lights, fans, and other electronics remotely, which forces them to return to their rooms or classrooms simply to switch appliances on or off, wasting valuable time and energy. Furthermore, many appliances are frequently left running without supervision, leading to excessive electricity consumption that not only wastes energy but also increases the risk of short circuits. The situation is worsened by the lack of real-time monitoring tools, preventing students from tracking the actual energy usage of specific appliances. Without such insights, they are unable to manage energy consumption efficiently, resulting in higher electricity costs and limited awareness of responsible energy usage practices. This highlights the urgent need for smarter solutions to improve both energy efficiency and safety within the dormitory environment.

Thus, the purpose of this paper is to build a system called Smart Extension Plug (SMEP) that can control and monitor connected electrical appliances via a smartphone application to reduce energy usage. Smart Extension Plug (SMEP) enables users to control and monitor connected electrical appliances via a smartphone application (F. Sanchez-Sutil 2023, Samson, 2020). In addition, SMEP

provides greater convenience and safety to users while helping to reduce electricity wastage through features such as remote control, energy usage monitoring and device status detection.

In line with technological advancements, the SMEP concept based on IoT technology is introduced to provide a safer and more efficient solution. SMEP enables real-time energy usage monitoring and controlling through a mobile application. In addition, it is equipped with an automatic safety system capable of detecting overloads and alerting users in the event of abnormal energy consumption. SMEP is expected to minimise the risks of fire and electrical appliance damage, while also enhancing the awareness of college students on the importance of safe and efficient energy consumption.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

SMEP uses the relay to safely control electrical or electronic appliances using signals from microcontrollers such as ESP32 or Arduino. Key features of the relay include excellent electrical insulation, protection against high current, and the ability to handle both AC and DC loads. The next important device included in SMEP is the ESP-32, which is equipped with a high-performance dual-core processor and various other features such as digital and analogue input/output, as well as support for multiple communication protocols like SPI, I2C and UART, including built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth connectivity. The Sensor ACS712 is used to measure electrical current in a circuit, whether alternating current (AC) or direct current (DC). This sensor utilises Hall Effect technology, which allows current to be measured without the need to connect wires directly to the circuit, making it safer and easier to use (Mona Berlian Sari, 2020).

Next, the ZMPT101B AC Voltage Sensor plays an important role in real-time voltage monitoring, providing critical information about energy usage and is equipped with an operational amplifier that converts AC voltage signals into analogue signals, which can then be read by microcontrollers such as ESP32 or Arduino. Besides that, the SMATRUL Tuya Switch Smart Life provides easy remote control and monitoring of electrical devices. SMEP is also included with a breadboard for connecting components such as microcontrollers, relays and sensors, and jumper wires for connecting components such as the ESP32, relay and current and voltage sensors on a breadboard.

In addition, the other hardware modules used to develop SMEP as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. SMEP Hardware Module Function.

No	Name	Description
1	5VDC 1-Way Channel Relay Active High	Allows low-power devices to control high-power equipment
2	ESP-32	To connect Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Low power consumption mode
3	ACS712 AC/DC Current Sensor	Helps to easily monitor the energy usage of electrical appliances
4	ZMPT101B AC Voltage Sensor	Helps to monitor electrical voltage in real time
5	SMATRUL Tuya Switch Smart Life	Provides easy remote control and monitoring of electrical devices
6	Breadboard	Connecting components such as microcontrollers, relays and sensors
7	Jumper Wire	Connecting components such as the ESP32, relay and current and voltage sensors on a breadboard.

Figure 1 shows the SMEP physical connection circuit and Figure 2 shows the SMEP in a circuit drawing connecting all the hardware modules. SMEP was next placed in a casing to secure the hardware components.

Figure 1. SMEP physical connection circuit.

Figure 2. SMEP circuit.

Figure 3 shows the completed SMEP was assembled using tools and materials such as an enclosure box, double-sided tape, hot melt glue gun, soldering tool and other suitable items.

Figure 3. Bulid and installation SMEP.

Figure 4. SMEP Placement Floor Plan.

Figure 4 illustrates the device's placement during testing, which was conducted in a college dormitory. The SMEP monitoring system was positioned on the far-left corner of a low floor table for user convenience, allowing easy placement of items like laptops and phones. The system is powered by an ESP32 microcontroller, with its control code written and tested in the Arduino IDE. It integrates a ZMPT101B voltage sensor and an ACS712 current sensor to monitor the SMEP's electrical parameters. All data is sent via Wi-Fi to the Blynk application, which provides a smartphone interface for real-time monitoring and includes a remote on/off switch function.

In the Blynk app, the Virtual Pins to the datastreams tab were added: VOLTAGE_VPIN (V0), CURRENT_VPIN (V1), POWER_VPIN (V2), and MENTOL_VPIN (V3), which should be configured as a switch widget, as in Figure 5. Create four widgets on the dashboard: three Gauge widgets for 'Voltage Level', 'Current Level', and 'Power Level', and one switch widget in Figure 6. Once the widgets and

virtual pins are set up in the Blynk application, the user can monitor consumption and control the electrical power in real-time, as in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows a testing session conducted by users to test the SMEP's functionality and to obtain feedback. The testing aims to ensure that the SMEP functions efficiently and that any problems or errors within the system can be identified and rectified before it is deployed to end-users. The tests conducted include performance, durability and system compatibility assessments to verify its operation with connected devices as well as to ensure a seamless interaction with the Blynk application.

Figure 5. Template setting in the Blynk.

Figure 6. Create 4 widgets.

Figure 7. Widgets and virtual pins are set up.

Figure 8. SMEP testing process by college users.

In a nutshell, SMEP is a project developed to produce an efficient smart extension plug that allows users to control electrical devices through a smartphone application as well as monitor and analyse energy consumption. This project aims to reduce energy waste and enhance user safety through the use of digital and communication technology.

3. FINDINGS

Smart Extension Plug (SMEP) is a very useful product for making it easy for users to control electrical appliances, providing real-time voltage and amperage data to help users control energy waste, timer and control functions that help manage energy usage more efficiently. Product testing determines whether a product function properly. Researchers have collected surveys from thirty-six (36) respondents to test the functionality of SMEP for users for possible improvements that can improve the quality of this product to work better and efficiently and also to overcome the number of cases resulting in the fire incidents and short circuits.

Table 2. Survey results.

No	Item	Percentage (%)
1	Less risks – short circuit & fire incident	72.2
2	Monitor consumption and control the electrical power	88.9
3	Prevent the carelessness of forgetting to turn off a switch	86.1
4	Energy management efficiency	72.0

Table 2 shows the overall results from the respondents for four questions asked of them. All the questions recorded responses ranging from 70% to 90% which indicates positive satisfaction from the respondents. The respondents agreed this product helps to reduce wasted energy. In addition, respondents believe that SMEP is very easy to manage and suits the needs of college students out there. It is not just because of the cost itself, but also because of the aspects of installation setup. Last but not least, it can be concluded that the functionality of this SMEP is in good condition and is capable of operating correctly.

4. DISCUSSION

Overall, throughout the development of this project, three main goals have been successfully achieved within the context of its use in a college dormitory. First, the system was designed to enable remote control of electrical equipment such as laptops, mobile phones and other electronic devices via a mobile application, providing convenience and flexibility to the residents. Second, the SMEP system also developed a real-time energy consumption monitoring and control function which serves to help users at the college control and manage their electricity usage more efficiently. Third, system testing has demonstrated the application's ability to display real-time energy usage data such as voltage and amperage, providing students with important information about the amount of energy being consumed at the plug. These results prove the project's effectiveness in achieving its goal of integrating IoT technology to improve electrical energy management, specifically at the college dormitory. However, after detailed testing, several advantages and disadvantages of the product were identified. The following is a brief summary of the product's strengths and weaknesses:

a) Advantages

- It allows users to easily control electrical equipment, such as laptops and mobile phones, through a mobile application.
- It provides real-time voltage and current data to help users control energy waste.
- The timer and control functions help manage energy consumption more efficiently.

b) Disadvantages

- It requires a stable internet connection to function properly.
- The development and component costs were relatively high for a prototype trial.
- Further improvements are needed, such as a more compact size and the addition of a safety cover.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the SMEP project has successfully achieved its primary goal of developing a more efficient and practical system for controlling and monitoring electrical energy consumption. Through the integration of IoT technology, this system enables remote control of electrical equipment like laptops and mobile phones via a mobile application as well as provides real-time monitoring of energy usage. Furthermore, this product also offers the benefit of increasing user awareness regarding energy consumption, thereby contributing to energy savings and more efficient management practices. Although there were several challenges and shortcomings, the proposed improvements discussed will ensure the project is enhanced in terms of functionality, design, and reliability. Overall, the SMEP not only benefits the residents of the college but also has the potential to be applied in various other contexts to improve energy efficiency.

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